

Hostel Allocation System: Beyond the First Come First Serve Technique

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Abstract— Abstract— The huge improvement of wireless services and the growth of web applications have drawn the attention of major sectors including the educational sector which have tried to solve to students challenges with the help of web applications and other application software. Hostel accommodation system has evolved from the traditional approach to the current state where students are automatically allocated to rooms by a software system either based on a first come first serve basis or in a randomized manner. Incompatibility of roommates is still an issue with the current allocation system. This has stimulated this research which aimed at developing a Personality-Based Hostel Allocation System (PHAS) where students are allocated to rooms based on their temperaments. The study adopted Eric Jorgenson's open four temperament scale test to develop a sorting algorithm which judiciously detects and allocate students to available rooms within the hostel accommodation. A PHAS model was designed which could be adopted by education institutions with hostel facilities. However, algorithms to allocate students to bed spaces or other hostel facilities can be considered as future works.

Keywords- Hostel Allocation System, Personality Traits, Temperaments, Eric Jorgenson

I. INTRODUCTION

Many institutions of learning have hostel accommodation for their respective students within or outside the campus. A hostel is a building that provides shelter, and lodging facilities to students – it could be a place of shelter, refuge, comfort, security, and dignity [1]. A Hostel is a fee-oriented dormitory that hold travellers or groups for a small period and provides basic amenities of a house [2]. A hostel could also mean shared accommodation. Instead of staying in a private room with a private bathroom, you stay in a dorm room with other people. Allocation of hostel accommodation among students must be effectively done to guarantee the ideal utilization of resources and the fulfillment of necessities and conditions. According to [3] the allocation of hostel has both economic and welfare effects for the development of a society.

The huge improvement of wireless services and the growth of web applications have drawn the attention of major sectors. As a result of this, business firms, producers, and service providers have continually sought to reach their consumers in various communities through various web technology platforms including through a web-based interactive Hostel Allocation System (HAS) as utilized by educational institutions [4]. Both private and government-owned institutions have sought effective ways of ensuring their students are allocated into hostels, halls, and rooms of their choice without uttering the effective functions of the institution as a whole. Alongside this, the revolution of software development has provided rising opportunities and need for a software application that creates instant registration through information derived from students' entry to secure favourable hostel accommodation [5].

At the primitive stage, many higher institutions were often involved in manual registration to allocate students in different hostel accommodations. In the advent of computerization, this old system became non-existence making some Nigerian universities wake up from their slumbers to face reality. It is worthy to note that computerization is a strong tool to combat the old and manual process of hostel allocation. Most University has witnessed remarkable growth in students' population that has created much concern for the management of the universities. In some Nigerian universities, the allocation of students into hostels is narrow in nature requiring students going to the Students' Affairs Office to fill out forms that seek to find out details of the students, provide a bank teller receipt to show payment, transfer of students' profiles to porter's lodge to receive mattress, pillow, and other relevant items as deemed fit by the institution - a process carried out with pen and papers which is unreliable with inefficiencies and a waste of time. There has been a step further in research where a software system is developed to automatically allocate students to hostel either based on a first come first serve basis or in a randomized manner. This often brings about incompatibility issues among roommates which could further instigate violence due to misunderstanding among them. This, therefore, makes it

imperative for schools to create a platform that would allocate students into hostels automatically with consideration of each student's personality such as hot, quick, active, extroverts, introverts, independent, courageous, noisy, quiet, vigilant, domineering, disciplined, and so on. There are weaknesses of the traditional manual hostel registration process such as, time consumption for both students and staff, misplacement, or damaging of files as a result of a movement from one point to another. Additionally, it is not convenient for both staff and students as the process is both tedious and stressful, but the main set back of the current system is the lack of interest in the compatibility of students before the allocation of room space.

Hence, this research work will be tailored towards developing an automated HAS based on the student's personality. The study aims to design a Personality-Based Hostel Allocation System (PHAS) for universities by proposing a personality sorting algorithm and PHAS framework. This was achieved through the adoption of Eric Jorgenson's open four temperament scale test into the proposed algorithm. An extensive review of existing HAS will be carried out to understand the current state of HAS. The purpose of this research work is to probe into developing a hostel allocation software for the university based on students' personalities considering current technological advancement. This system will not be a platform for payment of school fees, managing various activities in the hostels, the printing of course forms and result checking. This study would be beneficial to universities as a whole in creating awareness to allocate students into hostel through online software based on their personalities, welfare, and compatibilities, especially in their academics.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section discusses the theoretical framework and the review of related literatures.

A. Theoretical Framework of the Analytic Hierarchy Theory

1980. This process suggested by Saaty is quite often is referred to as "the Saaty method of Analytic Hierarchy Process" [6]. It is widely accepted by many individuals in a wide range of applications, especially in decision making. This theory describes the case applications ranging from the choice of selecting a hostel, school, and so on within the academic setting and learning environment. The analytic hierarchy process, also called AHP is variegated for decision making. For a good number of decision factors, the method is very suitable. It also allows for an organized method to hierarchically sort decision variables. However, it is clear from studies that, Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Multi-Attribute Decision Theory (MADT) are very similar. Moreover, [5] conclude that AHP is more straight forward. Meanwhile, he has submitted that AHP provides decision-makers the liberty to present a problem in a layered architecture highlighting the link between general regulations of AHP aims, objectivism, and alternatives.

The regulations of AHP require that choice options are orderly arranged as shown in Fig. 1. The first layer which is the in order of hierarchy represents the main aim which is the reason for the chosen student's hostel model, the second layer is broadly for the four main requirements which justify the selection of halls or hostels. What succeeds next is the level which shows the four (4) necessities for choosing students' hostel/hall— Nearness to lecture theatre (NT), students' compatibility (SC), Hostel Accommodation Cost (HAC) and Room Capacity (RC) which are proposed in this research. Lastly, the third layer shows two (2) categories of students for hostel allocation, these are new students and returning students.

The population explosion rate of students and most Nigerian university paradigm shifts gave rise to the spontaneous development of an automatic hostel management system. Research corroborated the above by stating that the sitting and expansion of Nigerian universities have attracted students to live in the school's hostel resulting in increased academic achievement. Student hostel has struck the core of the hearts of higher institutions due to the escalated interest in learning throughout the world [8]. Globally, student enrolment in higher institutions has been increasing in recent times, and it is estimated that there have been about a 160% increase in tertiary education globally [9]. HAS seeks to simplify the students' affairs, activities, and operation on the hostel portal. The traditional method of hostel allocation is time-consuming and not cost-friendly.

B. Review of Related Works

A General Framework Design for e-Hostel Allocation System was designed at the college of Alamanda, by [10]. The problem was that the number of students enrolling every year was always increasing which results in manual registration of accommodation problems. The specific objective was to study and demonstrates the general architecture of the e-Hostel Allocation System and to compose a set of online modules such as Staff Registration, Student Identification, Web Portal Administration, Student Allocation Generation & Report and also UNIMAS Colleges Integration (UCI) modules. The System analysis and methodology were object-oriented design. During the course of this project, they found that the system was able to demonstrate e-hostel allocation system and improved the prototype composition set of online modules such as staff registration, student identification, web portal administration, and student allocation generation and report, but the design of this study did not focus on students individual preferences and personal characteristics. [11] designed and Implementation of a Hostel Management System for Lagos State University (LASU). The researchers established the problem, stating that the existing hostel procedure for students' allocation was manual which is associated with inadequacies as more personnel are often required and a lot of times are wasted. Therefore, the objective was to implement an electronic hostel management system that will streamline registration process, reduce administrative tasks and paper work so as to improve the registration cycle process flow.

Figure 1. AHP in Selection of Students' Hostel

Hypertext Pre-processor (PHP) and MySQL database were used to implement the research work. It was found that the Electronic hostel management system for student's registration increased the speed of the registration. Yet again, the design of this study incorporates students who incompatible in the same room.

More research was done by [12], they designed a Hostel Management System for students' accommodation problems in Federal Colleges of Education in South-Eastern Nigeria. The researcher discovered that most hostels were too crowded, poorly built, and lack proper manual registration procedure. The specific objective was to find out the nature of student's hostel accommodation problems in the Federal Colleges of Education, find out the implications of accommodation problems on academic performance of students in these colleges, and Identify management strategies that could be adopted to improve on student's accommodation issues in these Federal Colleges of Education. This was achieved by adopting a descriptive survey design. In the project, his major findings showed that the student agreed that inadequate hostel accommodation, overcrowding, were due to bad allocation system. The deficiency in this study was the adoption of a questionnaire that is prone to wrong feedbacks. Furthermore, [13] designed and implemented a computerized HAS at Ogun state institute of technology. The researcher stated that the Problems associated with hostel records are the manual situation by the University system which resulted in the development of an application that will ease the stress associated with the existing manual system. However, the research still did not address the problem of shared control over choice of room amongst students.

[14] designed an Online Hostel Management System to address the complex task of managing student data and hostel allocation by the manual system was time-consuming. The

objective was to develop a hostel management system that manages all the data related to students like name, parent's name, contact number, email, and address. The researchers discovered an efficient way of building the System using object-oriented designs alongside PHP-MySQL source code which would help in developing the online Hostel Management System. Furthermore, [15] designed a Student Residence Management System. The problem addressed was the manual registration for accommodation which is quite difficult most especially for students that are in distant areas who cannot reach the university. Paper-based registration consumes time. The study failed to develop HAS based on the students' characters.

Critically Studying previous researchers' works and designs of hostel management systems, it has been very clear that they all have one thing in common, that is, the alleviation of students from the bottlenecks and rigmarole involved in the process of getting a space in a hall or hostel through the adoption of the best technology. However, the job is half complete. If the purpose for which all previous researchers developed their platform was to ease students live on campus, particularly in the area of hostel allocation, then it has to be a step further to look at the lives of students after the allocation of room space. We have to incorporate into what has been previously done, a personality sorting algorithm that would sufficiently allocate rooms to students on not just the basis of payment of hostel fees or school fees as the case may be with most higher institutions, but also based on compatibility. It is for this reason we have proposed a Personality-Based Hostel Allocation System (PHAS). A system that allocates new students into rooms based on their compatibility, using the best sorting algorithm. The hostel management system is a web application that is designed to manage different students, wardens, and administrator activities in the process of hostel registrations.

III. HUMAN PERSONALITY TRAITS

A personality sorting algorithm is an integral part of the software. This is achieved by formulating psychological questions to detect the behaviour of humans and categorizes them into various groups that logically belong in pairs. The purpose of this categorization is largely influenced by the need for any organization or institution seeking to understand the personality or temperament of an individual. In our case study, we are interested in sorting students into groups of four categories namely, Choleric, Melancholy, Sanguine, and Phlegmatic. The idea of the four temperaments traces back to the Ancient Greek medical theory of the four humours, which held that there were four fundamental bodily humours (blood, yellow bile, black bile, and phlegm) and that illness was caused by an imbalance in these. The terms are as follows; Sanguine, Choleric, Melancholic, and Phlegmatic. The temperaments were coined by the Greek physician Aelius Galenus to describe the effect of the humours on personality [16], [17]. These temperaments are explained below [18].

A. Sanguine

These set of people are fundamentally impulsive and pleasure-seeking, they are often referred to as the talker. They are a very social person who likes to be with people and the most impulsive of all the temperaments – friendly, outgoing, enthusiastic, and generally positive about life. The Sanguine will volunteer for difficult tasks and they will complete the tasks. The Sanguine is by far the most versatile of the four temperaments.

B. Choleric

The Choleric temperament is fundamentally ambitious and leader-like. The Choleric is the strongest of the extroverted, often referred to as “the doer” (or “the driver”). They are quick-thinking, peppy, actionable, self-sufficient, and very independent – visionaries and seem to never run out of ideas, ambitions, and intention. They tend not to be angry, but they are quickly aroused, and quickly calmed.

C. Melancholic

The Melancholic temperament is fundamentally introverted and thoughtful. They are often referred to as “the thinker.”. The Melancholy naturally wants to do things right, and is quality-oriented – they are not trying to be right; they are driven to figure out what is right. They very much rely on themselves and are independent. They are perfectionists.

D. Phlegmatic

The Phlegmatic temperament is fundamentally relaxed and quiet, ranging from warmly attentive to lazily sluggish. They are referred to as “the watcher”. They are best in positions of unity and mediation, and solid in positions that desire steadiness. They are shy and tend to prefer being stable. Phlegmatic live a quiet, routine life free of the normal anxieties of the other temperaments.

From the above description of the four basic temperaments of humans, it is clear that there is a need for administrators to

be very careful when allocating students with a certain type of temperament into rooms. In our proposed system, we are matching Choleric with Phlegmatic because from the above description, while a Choleric is extroverted, quick-thinking, active, practical, strong-willed, and easily annoyed, a Phlegmatic who isn't going to give much trouble, naturally easy-going is the best match that is Choleric-Phlegmatic. We can assert that the Sanguine has the potential for the widest range of behavior due to possessing the widest range of emotions, therefore, we conclude that the best match is a Melancholic who naturally wants to do things right, and is quality-oriented. Melancholies are not trying to be right; they are driven to figure out what is right.

IV. PERSONALITY SORTING ALGORITHM

To adequately decipher the temperaments of students to achieve the aim of this research, which is to find a compatible roommate for students, we have chosen to use Eric Jorgenson's Temperament Scales (as seen in Appendix I) because it removes the ambiguity that comes with other temperament scales such as Infant Toddler Temperament Tool (IT³) and so on. In 2014, Eric Jorgenson designed the Open Four Temperaments Scales [19]. In systems where there has not been a careful allocation process that sought to study the personalities of students before allocating rooms to them, the result would always be an ill-matching of students with different temperaments. Matching students with similar personalities can indeed lead to overfamiliarity which breeds contempt. However, the merits of having compatible personalities such as the proposed matching which are Choleric-Phlegmatic and Sanguine-Melancholic are Improved academic excellence, Happiness in the lives of students, Peace and tranquillity in the hostel and Unity amongst students.

The test consists of 48 statements that must be rated on how much you agree with them on a three-point scale (where Disagree = 1, Neutral = 3, and Agree = 5). The logic of each question is the same all through and it is that each question is tied to a pair of temperament (super trait temperament and weak trait temperament) either Choleric and Sanguine or Sanguine and Phlegmatic or Melancholic and Phlegmatic or Phlegmatic and Choleric or Sanguine and Melancholic or Choleric and Melancholic. If a student disagrees with a question, such a student score 2 points for the weak temperament in the pair. On the other contrary, if a student agrees with a question, such student scores 2 for the super-trait temperament in the pair. Therefore, disagreeing or agreeing with a question enshrines a student's temperaments (either of the pair but not both). The middle point in the scale scores the student 1 point each for both temperaments in the pair.

At the end of the test, upon submission, the scores are calculated and the highest score enshrines his most dominant temperament. In the event of a tie score for all temperament, the student will be assigned automatically to the Sanguine temperament because most people are of the sanguine temperament. To obtain the information needed in the allocation, all new students must take this test online after they

have selected their hostel of choice. After the test, the student's most dominant personality would be one of the four categories. This information would determine whether he or she is suitable for a room or not. It takes just five minutes for most people to take the test. The test questions are shown in appendix 1.

A. System Flow

Input: Student Score from Open Four Temperaments Scales Test

Output: Room Allocation Details

Step 1: Begin

Step 2: Declare: weakTraitValue, superTraitValue, question, i, temp_pairs, user_choice, studentTemp, tempName, availableRooms, max_lim_room, temp_of_occupant

Step 3: Repeat Step 4 for i = 0 to N-1 by 1:

Step 4: Read: question

Read: temp_pairs

Read: user_choice

If user_choice = 1, Then:

Read: weakTraitValue

Set weakTraitValue = 2

Else If user_choice = 5, Then:

Read: superTraitValue

Set superTraitValue = 2

Else

Read: weakTraitValue

Read: superTraitValue

Set weakTraitValue = 1

Set superTraitValue = 1

[End of Else-If]

[End of For Loop]

Step 5: studentTemp = max(TempName)

Step 6: Read: availableRooms, max_lim_room, student_TempId

Step 7: Repeat Step 8 for i = 0 to availableRooms-1 by 1:

Step 8: Read: no_of_occupants

If no_of_occupants = 0, Then:

Set availableRoom[i] = rand (studentTempId)

Else If (no_of_occupants > 0) && (no_of_occupants <= max_lim_room)

Read: temp_of_occupant

If (temp_of_occupant == C) || (temp_of_occupant == P), Then:

Set availableRoom[i] = studentTempId
WHERE studentTempId == C OR P

[End of If]

If (temp_of_occupant == S) || (temp_of_occupant == M), Then:

Set availableRoom[i] = studentTempId
WHERE studentTempId == S OR M

[End of If]

Else

i = i + 1

Set availableRoom[] = i

[End of Else-If]

Step 9: End

The key to interpreting the declared variables in the Algorithm are stated below:

1) *weakTraitValue*: This holds the actual temperament that represents the weak trait in the temperament pair for a particular question.

2) *superTraitValue*: This holds the actual temperament that represents the super trait in the temperament pair for a particular question.

3) *question*: This stores the question displayed to the user based on Eric Jorgenson's open four temperament scale test.

4) *i*: This is the counter to loop through the questions.

5) *temp_pairs*: This stores the pairs of temperament tied to a particular question – one represents the weak trait, the other represent the super trait based on the question.

6) *user_choice*: This holds the value of the student's answer to a question that could be Disagree (1), Neutral (3), or Agree (5).

7) *studentTemp*: This stores the actual temperament of the student after computation based on the student's response.

8) *tempName*: This stores the actual name of the temperaments which could be Sanguine, Melancholy, Choleric, or Phlegmatic.

9) *availableRooms*: This holds the total number of available rooms for allocation.

10) *max_lim_room*: This stores the maximum occupant of a room.

11) *temp_of_occupant*: This holds the temperaments of the current occupants of a room.

B. PHAS Model

The designed model which can be adopted by any institution or organization in allocating hostel accommodations is shown in Fig. 2. The steps involved in the model are explained below:

Step 1: The HAS is displayed based on the available source code.

Step 2: The HAS is the portal that the student will interact with. A lot of things can be done on the HAS including room allocation which is the focus of this research.

Step 3: The HAS interacts with the PHAS Application Programming Interface (API).

Figure 2. AHP in Selection of Students' Hostel

Step 4: The PHAS API detects if the student is a fresher or returning student. If the student is a fresher, such a student will be mandated to take the personality test to detect the student's temperament. However, if the student is a returnee, the student's temperament will be in the Database.

Step 5: The HAS interacts with the PHAS Application Programming Interface (API) to complete the allocation process. Both returning students and freshers will be allocated to a room with the help of the API.

Step 6: This denotes the successful completion of room allocation.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This research work successfully developed a PHAS framework that can be used by any University and serves as a means of

managing the affairs of hostel allocation in the best way possible. With this system, we can take care of the basic requirements of Hostel Management Systems. Since it has a personality sorting algorithm, new students can take the tests and be rest assured that they will be allocated a room space with a compatible roommate. Future researches might want to include the allocation of bed space and other hostel facilities to students on a first-come-first-served basis. This would buttress the point more to a higher degree, that the livelihood of students on campuses is the number one priority of this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Ademiluyi, "Public housing delivery strategies in Nigeria: A historical perspective of policies and programmes," *J. Sustain. Dev. Africa*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 153–161, 2010.

- [2] S. Edington, "Don't Be Hostile About Hostels," *Stripes Europe*, 2019. <https://europe.stripes.com/travel/dont-be-hostile-about-hostels> (accessed Jul. 28, 2020).
- [3] J. S. Babalola, A. I. Umar, and L. A. Sulaiman, "An Economic Analysis of Determinants of House Rents in The University Environment," *Eur. Sci. J.*, vol. 9, no. 19, pp. 1857–7881, 2013.
- [4] B. O. Owolabi, "The Effects of Students' Housing On Academic Performance At The University of Ibadan in Nigerian," *Int. J. Sci. Eng. Res.*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1118–1132, 2015.
- [5] D. B. Hammad, J. M. Musa, A. G. Rishi, and I. I. Ayuba, "Criteria for The Selection Of Students' Accommodation Model in Nigeria Tertiary Institutions Using Analytic Hierarchy Process," *Acad. Res. Int.*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 550–556, 2013.
- [6] F. Zahedi, "The Analytic Hierarchy Process—A Survey of the Method and its Applications," *Interfaces (Providence)*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 96–108, Aug. 1986, doi: 10.1287/inte.16.4.96.
- [7] O. Aluko, "The Assessment of Housing Situation among Students in the University of Lagos," *African Res. Rev.*, vol. 5, no. 3, 2011, doi: 10.4314/afrrv.v5i3.67345.
- [8] O. Adebisi, N. Ezeokoli, A. A. Oletubo, and T. J. Alade, "Rental Analysis of Residential Properties in Close Proximity to the Federal University of Technology , Akure , Nigeria," *J. Econ. Sustain. Dev.*, vol. 6, no. 10, pp. 140–147, 2015.
- [9] E. Attakora-amaniampong, A. Salakpi, and J. Y. Dwamena, "Analyzing Risk of Student Hostel Investment : The Case of Private Investors," *Int. J. Bus. Soc. Res.*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 43–56, 2014.
- [10] A. R. Mat and S. A. Abd Rahman, "A General Framework Design for e-Hostel Allocation System : A Case Study on Alamanda College," UNIMAS, 2006.
- [11] K. Ayanlowo, O. Shoewu, S. O. Olatinwo, O. O. Omitola, and D. D. Bablola, "Development of an Automated Hostel Facility Management System," *J. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2014, Accessed: Aug. 05, 2020. [Online]. Available: www.oricpub.com.
- [12] J. F. Gilbert, "Management of Students Hostel Accommodation Problems in Federal Colleges of Education in South Eastern Nigeria," University of Nigeria, 2011.
- [13] K. E. Omopariola and M. O. Tirimisiyu, "Design and Implementation of Computerized Hostel Allocation Management System," Ogun State Institute of Technology, 2015.
- [14] J. Yadav, V. Maurya, and M. Ojha, "Online Hostel Management System," *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 1–5, 2016, doi: 10.14445/23488387/ijcse-v3i4p101.
- [15] I. M. Louise, "Student Residence Management System," University of the Western Cape, 2009.
- [16] L. Peters, "What's Your Four Humors Personality Type?," *Bustle*, 2015. <https://www.bustle.com/articles/98094-whats-your-four-humors-personality-type-this-test-will-tell-you-whether-youre-sanguine-phlegmatic-choleric> (accessed Aug. 05, 2020).
- [17] R. M. Stelmack and A. Stalikas, "Galen and the humour theory of temperament," *Pers. Individ. Dif.*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 255–263, 1991, doi: 10.1016/0191-8869(91)90111-N.
- [18] D. W. Ekstrand, "The Four Human Temperaments," in *The Transformed Soul*, 2012.
- [19] T. Popomaronis, "Science Reveals One of These Cars Might Be Your Dream Vehicle," *Inc.*, 2016. <https://www.inc.com/tom-popomaronis/science-reveals-one-of-these-cars-might-be-your-dream-vehicle.html> (accessed Aug. 05, 2020).

APPENDIX I

This Appendix contains the Eric Jorgenson Open Four Temperaments Scales Test which will be presented to the students to get the dominant temperament.

1. I make people feel welcome (S, M)
2. I seldom feel blue (S, M)
3. The good life is a peaceful life (P, S)
4. I'd hate to live in the far north (C, S)
5. I would never attend therapy (P, C)
6. I tend to feel very hopeless (P, C)
7. I rarely get irritated (M, P)
8. I like it when people are scared of me (C, S)
9. I experience my emotions intensely (M, C)
10. I whistle when I walk (S, M)
11. I try to outdo others (C, P)
12. I boss people around (C, P)
13. I choose my words with care (P, M)
14. I feel attacked by others (P, C)
15. It is hard for me to imagine what having low self-esteem would be like (C, P)
16. I avoid arguments (M, S)
17. I never think much about how I look (M, S)
18. I daydream about being in love (S, C)
19. I don't care much when people insult me (M, S)
20. I lose my temper (M, P)
21. I tell other people my secrets (S, C)
22. I have a strong need for power (C, P)
23. I bet a lot of people with multiple personalities are just faking it (P, C)
24. I never slam the door (P, S)
25. I am the life of the party (S, M)
26. I should be more careful with my secrets (S, C)
27. I am relaxed most of the time (M, C)
28. I have had a dramatic falling out with a friend (C, M)
29. I'd not mind if I stopped receiving holiday gifts (P, S)
30. I radiate joy (S, P)
31. I prefer variety to routine (S, P)
32. I have not been jealous of anyone for quite some time (M, C)
33. I seldom get mad (P, M)
34. I am willing to take the risk to establish a relationship (C, P)
35. I slam doors (S, P)
36. I take a lot of abuse to get me angry (S, C)
37. I think about the cause of my emotions (C, M)
38. I make friends easily (S, M)
39. I try to please everyone (P, M)

40. I dance when I am alone (P, S)
41. I suffer from other's sorrows (S, M)
42. I feel my anxiety overwhelms me (P, C)
43. I get angry easily (M, P)
44. I feel comfortable with myself (C, P)
45. I would be very hurt if someone accused me of being uncaring (M, C)
46. I don't like getting gifts (M, S)
47. I feel jealousy as physical pain (M, C)
48. I use flattery to get ahead (S, P)

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